

Xlang: Type-Safe Generality Without Overhead – V3

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Xlang is a new statically typed multi-staged systems programming language with emphasis on code-reuse, efficiency, elegance, and effective software development. Xlang's generic programming – i.e., linguistic support for systematic code-reuse – is similar to Rust and Swift in its combination of C++ template-level performance and traits as constraints. That combination enables early type-checking of

generic code, serving the effectiveness of software development. Xlang's generic programming also features **unbounds**: a construct similar to ML's abstract types, which take contextuality beyond what is offered by Scala traits. **unbounds** make dependency injection—a resilient challenge in software development—elegant and lightweight. When employed for dependent-typing, **unbounds** are a means for static prevention of ownership bugs, serving effective software development in yet another new way. Finally, Xlang's novel precomputation stage automatically offers to the everyday programmer efficiency that is even beyond the reach of C/C++.

Section 1. Lightweight and Effective Code Reuse

Section 1.1. Definition-Checked Templates

Programming with C++ templates, although invaluable, comes at a very high price. From a software-development perspective, a major contributor to that high price is the late support for error detection.¹ Little error detection is available before a template is instantiated, if any at all. That leaves the programmer of a template (as opposed to its user) with little linguistic support. And, it is too late and unhelpful for the user of a template to be informed of an error made by the programmer of the template.

In [Listing 1](#), the function `fn` does not advertise its requirement for instances of its type parameter `T` to be invocable with member functions `f()`, `g()`, and `f(bool)`. However, C++ templates are deliberately designed so if the type substituted for `T` supports such invocations, the instantiation is admissible. Otherwise, only the instantiation, and not the definition, is faulty. That is why the error is only detected at the instantiation on line 19 of [Listing 1](#). Yet, that error detection may be totally unhelpful. `S2`'s user might have no idea about what is inside `fn` and why the invocation on the last line might relate to the lack of invocability of `s2` using a member function `f()`, `g()`, and `f(bool)`.

[Listing 1](#). Instantiation-Checked Template in C++

```
01  template<typename T> void fn(T t) {
02      t.f();
03      t.g();
04      t.f(false);
05  }
06
07  // fn-user's code -- different from that of fn-programmer
08  struct S1 {
09      void f(bool = true) {}
10      void g() {}
11  };
12
13  struct S2 {};
```

¹ Amongst the systems programming languages, Rust and Swift predate *Xlang* in that mindset.

```

15 S1 s1;
16 S2 s2;
17
18 fn(s1);
19 fn(s2); // Error! No member function f(), g(), or f(bool) in S2

```

The Xlang templates have similar efficiency to the C++ ones. They too are completely compile-time. However, their type-checking is done upon definition. An important Xlang ingredient for that is traits. [Listing 2](#) contains a trait `Tau`, which **only** has a function `f` in its interface that can only be called without any argument and that returns an `int32`. Therefore, inside the body of the function `fn`, only calling a member function `f` on an instance of `Tau` is allowed, and only with no argument. Otherwise, compilation fails with errors such as those on lines 08 and 09 of [Listing 2](#). Note that all this is before the function `fn` is instantiated.

[Listing 2. Definition-Checked Templates in X](#)

```

01 trait Tau {
02     int32 f();
03 }
04
05 void fn(type T <: Tau)(T t) {
06     t.f();
07     t.g(); // Error! g not in Tau's interface
08     t.f(true); // Error! f(bool) not in Tau's interface
09 }

```

Section 1.1.1 What about C++ Concepts?

The reader might think that C++20 Concepts could have prevented the issue. That, however, is not true. Consider `fn_with_con` in [Listing 3](#), which is the Concepts-armed counterpart of `fn` in [Listing 1](#). `fn_with_con` is still permissible; no compile error for that function. Such is also the instantiation of `fn_with_con` with `s1`, even though `Tau` does not require the invocability of `t` as on lines 07 and 08 in `fn_with_con`. The only difference is that, for the invocation of `fn_with_con` with `s2`, the compiler states that `S2` does not comply with the requirements of `Tau`. That is because, even with Concepts, C++ templates are (almost) only checked upon instantiation.²

[Listing 3. fn of Listing 1 with Concepts](#)

```

01 template<typename T> concept Tau = requires(T t) {
02     { t.f() } -> void;

```

² See Section 1.1.3 of [“C++ Templates”](#) for more.

```

03 }
04
05 template<Tau T> void fn_with_con(T t) { // Compiles successfully!
06     t.f();
07     t.g();
08     t.f(false);
09 }
10
11 fn_with_con(s1); // Still compiles successfully!
12 fn_with_con(s2); // Error! S2 does not fulfill the requirements of Tau.

```

Section 1.2. Elegant Dependency Injection

Dependency injection is a resilient challenge in software development. Programmers of different languages have crafted different solutions for dependency injection. There are a plethora of dependency-injection solutions available in C++, for example.

[Listing 4](#) showcases an example `SceneObject`³ from a simple game application, which delegates its logging, rendering, and handling of physics to its data members predesignated for those purposes. That is a typical dependency-injection situation. `SceneObject` does not construct its own logging, rendering, or physics media. Instead, its constructor receives (pointers to) instances of the respective types (`Logger`, `Renderer`, and `PhysicsSystem`) for the respective jobs (lines 02–04).

Listing 4. Example Dependency Injection in C++

```

01 struct SceneObject {
02     Logger*      m_logger;
03     Renderer*   m_renderer;
04     PhysicsSystem* m_physics;
05
06     SceneObject(Logger* logger, Renderer* renderer, PhysicsSystem* physics) :
07         m_logger{logger}, m_renderer{renderer}, m_physics{physics} {...}
08
09     void Log() { m_logger->Log(this); }
10     void Draw() { m_renderer->Draw(this); }
11     void Update(float delta) { m_physics->Update(this, delta); }
12 }

```

The game play typically also involves many other game objects. Despite their variety, such game objects often share some of their dependencies. For example, it is likely that the logger is shared

³ The “`Object`” trailing part of the name “`SceneObject`” does not indicate objects in their OOP sense. On the contrary, “`Object`” in that context – i.e., in the context of the gaming industry – is an object in the game.

amongst all the objects in a scene. Here are a few ways to ensure the sameness of the shared dependencies:

- making them global and accepting to suffer from all the downsides of global variables.
- passing them around all the time so, in every context, the dependency of discourse is itself present and determines the “correct” dependency for every important party.
- Using C++ `namespaces`. However, even though `namespaces` are designed for grouping, amongst their other problems, they provide write access to every other constituent of the code. In other words, `namespace`-scoped variables are only slightly restricted global variables with almost all their downsides.

In *Xlang*, `unbounds` serve as an elegant means for dependency injection. In [Listing 5](#), the *Xlang* `SceneObject` declares its dependency to the logger, renderer, and physics system using `unbounds` (lines 02–05). Note first that `unbounds` are not data members (static or not). As a result, `SceneObject`'s constructor is now trivial and does not even need to be mentioned any longer. (That saves the *Xlang* `SceneObject` lines 06 and 07 of [Listing 4](#).) The other *Xlang* feature demonstrated in [Listing 5](#) is `zones`. A `zone` is similar to a C++ `namespace`. However, a `zone` does not give write access to its bindings. Every `unbound` can only be bound once in a given scope, and a `zone` introduces a scope. In [Listing 5](#), the bindings in the first three lines of `LowFi` (i.e., lines 12–14) are shared amongst all the `SceneObjects` in the entire `zone`. After all, the *Xlang* policy of uniqueness of bindings per `unbound` per scope implies no other binding for `m_logger`, `m_renderer`, and `m_physics` elsewhere in `LowFi`. (Contrary to that, in the C++ world, every constituent of the code can alter the contents of a `namespace` counterpart of `LowFi`.)

Listing 5. The *Xlang* Equivalent of Listing 4 and the Elegance of **unbound** as a Means for Dependency Injection

```
01 struct SceneObject {
02     unbound Logger      m_logger;
03     unbound Renderer    m_renderer;
04     unbound PhysicsSystem m_physics;
05
06     void Log() { m_logger->Log(this); }
07     void Draw() { m_renderer->Draw(this); }
08     void Update(float delta) { m_physics->Update(this, delta); }
09 }
10
11 zone LowFi {
12     FileLogger fileLogger; // FileLogger implements the Logger trait
13     FlatRenderer flatRenderer; // FlatRenderer implements the Renderer trait
14     BoxPhysics boxPhysics; // BoxPhysics implements the PhysicsSystem trait
15
16     bind SceneObject.m_logger => fileLogger;
17     bind SceneObject.m_renderer => flatRenderer;
18     bind SceneObject.m_physics => boxPhysics;
19     // The entire zone now shares the above bindings, without requiring any repetition.
20     // There is no write access to the above bindings from outside.
21     // The bindings above are read-only hereafter within the zone.
22     ...
23 }
24
25 zone HighFi {
26     CloudLogger cloudLogger; // CloudLogger implements the Logger trait
27     RayTraceRenderer rayTracer; // RayTraceRenderer impls the Renderer trait
28     RigidBodyPhysics rigidBodyPhysics; // RigidBodyPhysics impls the PhysicsSystem trait
29
30     bind SceneObject.m_logger => cloudLogger;
31     bind SceneObject.m_renderer => rayTracer;
32     bind SceneObject.m_physics => rigidBodyPhysics;
33     ...
34 }
```

Section 1.3. Undemanding Contextuality for **unbounds**

Xlang statically ensures that all **unbounds** are bound at any point where they may be used at runtime. Trying to use an **unbound** in a scope where no **bind**-for the **unbound is accessible** is a compile-error. When in competition, the precedence between the different bindings available to a scope is determined by locality of scope and then the call chain. That is where the contextuality of **bind**-resolution becomes visible. The **bind** that is closest to the usage site on the call chain wins over

the rest (in the absence of local `binds`). Such a `bind` is said to `bind` tighter than the rest. For example, in [Listing 6](#), in the call chain `z.f3() → z.f1() → z.g()` the `bind` in `f1` for `S.v` wins over that of `f3` because, there is no `bind` for `S.v` in `g`, and `f1` is closer to `g` than `f3` on the call chain.

Listing 6. `unbound` Type `T` and `unbound` Value `v` with their Bindings

```
01 struct S {
02     unbound type      T;
03     unbound Vector<int16> v;
04 }
05
06 struct Z {
07     bind S.T => float64;
08     void f1() {
09         Vector<int16> this_v = {1, 2};
10         ...
11         bind S.v => this_v;
12         g();
13     }
14     void f2() {
15         Vector<int16> that_v = {1, 2, 3};
16         ...
17         bind S.v => that_v;
18         g();
19     }
20     void f3() {
21         Vector<int16> v = {1, 2, 3, 4};
22         ...
23         bind S.v => v;
24         f1(); // <-- ***
25     }
26     void g() {
27         println(S.v.length());
28     }
29 }
30
31 int64 main() {
32     Z z;
33     z.f1(); // prints 2
34     z.f2(); // prints 3
35     z.f3(); // still prints 2 (as opposed to 4)
36             // Z.f1 binds S.v tighter in the call-stack
37     z.g();  // Compile-error! S.v not bound in Z.g
38 }
```

There are **unbound** types and **unbound** values, as shown in [Listing 6](#). The **unbound** type of `S` called `T` can be bound to types (line 02). **unbound** types are similar to the abstract types of SML or the abstract type members of Scala. The **unbound** value `v` of `S` (line 03) can be bound to instances of `Vector(int16)`. On the other hand, **unbound** values are a sort of middle ground between global variables and Scala's contextual parameters. Examining [Listing 6](#) in more detail will illustrate why.

In [Listing 6](#), the struct `Z` binds the **unbound** type `T` of the struct `S` (line 07). Yet, it does not bind the **unbound** value `v` of `S`. Nevertheless, its member function `g` is able to access `S.v` without error (line 27). This is because *Xlang* observes that every call to `g` is made within a scope that does bind `S.v`; Or, it will issue a compile-error. In other words, *Xlang* implicitly parameterizes `g` by `S.v` and tries to implicitly provide the argument to that parameter at each call to `g`.

Thus, conceptually, **unbounds** are specified *contextually* rather than explicitly. This makes them much more convenient to use when shared across large parts of a code base, but also much more flexible to use than global type aliases or program variables. Furthermore, *Xlang*'s type system ensures that **unbounds** are used safely throughout the program and consistently across related program elements.

The contextuality of **bind**-resolution is an important design decision in *Xlang*:

- It allows for a particularly **memory-efficient** implementation of **unbounds**. In *Xlang*, **unbounds** are hidden parameters to the functions of a call chain. For example, the `z.f3() → z.f1() → z.g()` chain is rather `z.f3(✖) → z.f1(this_v) → z.g(this_v)` internally. (The argument "v" in `z.f3(✖)` is not mistakenly struck through. That notation indicates that the bindee "v" for `S.v` is outdated by the **bind** of next functions on the chain. In this case, what outdates "v" is "this_v" of `z.f1`, which binds tighter.) See [Section 1.5](#) for more information on the memory-efficiency of **unbounds**.
- It allows for an easy and deterministic **bind**-resolution algorithm. For example, in `if(condition) bind ub => this_ub else bind ub => that_ub,` would it not be for the contextuality, the bindee of `ub` would have been `{this_ub, that_ub}`. Whereas, given the contextuality of **unbounds**, one can determine the exact winning **bind** in each branch of the **if**-statement without the need for taking the runtime value of the condition into consideration.

unbound values are similar to abstract **vals** of Scala (from one point of view) and also contextual parameters of Scala (from another point of view). However, in comparison to those competitors of theirs, the *Xlang* **unbounds** are particularly undemanding. In short, that is because **unbounds** can be declared in every scope and bound in every other scope (only once, however, and subject to accessibility). Here is the comparison in more detail:

- An abstract type in SML can only be declared in a **signature** and made concrete in a **structure** that implements that **signature**.
- An abstract **val** in Scala can only be declared in a **trait**. It can then be overridden only in an **object** or a **class** that extends the **trait** or provided by another **trait** that mixes in.

- A contextual parameter in Scala is only available to functions or classes. Provision of a `given` instance for a contextual parameter is as undemanding as an *Xlang* `bind`.

Section 1.4. Static Prevention of Ownership Bugs

A mistake in working with C++ iterators is comparison between iterators over different containers. On line 02 of [Listing 7](#), the beginning iterator of `first` is sent to `sort` along with the ending iterator of `second`.

[Listing 7. Sending Iterators of Different Containers as a Range to a C++ STL Algorithm](#)

```
01  vector<int> first, second;
02  sort(first.begin(), second.end());
```

Even though `[first.begin(), second.end())` does not constitute a valid range, C++ cannot detect that and the above code will create an infinite loop, possibly also causing a segmentation fault. That is because a `vector<int>::iterator` (if not a raw pointer itself) owns a pointer to the container it is iterating over and the pointee of that member of `vector<int>::iterator` does NOT participate in the type of the `vector<int>::iterator`.

On the contrary, provided that an *Xlang* iterator is implemented using `unbounds` like in [Listing 8](#), the *Xlang* equivalent of line 02 in [Listing 7](#) would fail to type-check.

[Listing 8. Using `unbounds` for Implementing Iterators in X and Avoiding the Bug in \[Listing 7\]\(#\)](#)

```
01  struct iterator(type T) {
02    unbound vector(T) container;
03    ...
04  }
05
06  struct vector(type T) {
07    ...
08    bind iterator(T).container => this; // <-- ***
09    iterator(T) begin() const;
10    iterator(T) end() const;
11  }
12
13  vector(int16) first, second;
14  sort(first.begin(), second.end()); // compile-error!
15                                     // first.begin().type == first:iterator(int16),
16                                     // whereas
                                     // second.end().type == second:iterator(int16)
```

Instead of a pointer to the container it is iterating over, the `iterator` in [Listing 8](#) has an `unbound` of type `vector(T)` on line 02. Inside the body of `vector`, then that `unbound` is bound to the `vector` the iterator will be iterating over. Note how, on line 08 of [Listing 8](#), `iterator(T).container` is bound to an instance-specific entity of `vector` – namely, `this`. Given that instance-specific binding, in addition to being of type `iterator(T)`, what `vector.begin` and `vector.end` return have instance-specific types. That `bind` is universal to the entire body of `vector(T)`. As a consequence, `first.begin()`'s type is `first:iterator(int16)` (read as: an iterator of `int16`s that iterates over `first`). On the contrary, `second.end()`'s type is `second:iterator(int16)` (read as: an iterator of `int16`s that iterates over `second`). That is how the call to `sort` on line 13 of [Listing 8](#) is a compile-error: The two iterators sent to `sort` have different types. `sort`, however, expects them to have the same type, as shown in [Listing 9](#).

[Listing 9](#). Type Signature of `sort` in `X`

```
void sort(type T)(iterator(T) b, iterator(T) e) {...}
```

Note that, in [Listing 9](#), `b` and `e` are **implicitly** taken to have the same binding for `container:iterator(T)` for some `container`. We refer to that as the `bind-sameness` assumption. Were that assumption not implicit, `sort`'s signature would have been required to be what is in [Listing 10](#). In fact, [Listing 9](#) is a shorter version of [Listing 10](#). In other words, [Listing 10](#) is also valid `Xlang`.

[Listing 10](#). Type Signature of `sort` with Explicit Binding for `iterator(T).container`

```
void sort(type T)(vector(T) v)(v:iterator(T) b, v:iterator(T) e) {...}
```

Section 1.4.1. More Advanced `bind`-Sameness

Sometimes, there is no need to enforce `bind-sameness`. For example, consider the [Listing 11](#) overload of the `std::set_difference` algorithm of the C++ STL.

[Listing 11](#). An Overload of `std::set_difference` of the C++ STL

```
template<typename InputIt1, typename InputIt2, typename OutputIt>
OutputIt set_difference(InputIt1 first1, InputIt1 last1,
                       InputIt2 first2, InputIt2 last2, OutputIt
                       d_first);
```

In [Listing 11](#),

- `first1` and `last1` are required to iterate over the same container.
- `first2` and `last2` are also required to iterate over the same container. But, there is no requirement for the container of this bullet to be the same as that of the previous bullet. And,

- `d_first` is not required to iterate over either of the containers of the previous bullets.

C++ has no means for imposing the above. In *Xlang*, the programmer instructs the compiler to impose the above `bind`-sameness requirements at compile-time as in [Listing 12](#). For example, the first bullet above is imposed by type of both `first1` and `last1` to be `v1::iterator(T1)`. Here is the key extra type ingredient, in comparison to their C++ counterparts:

- In the C++ version, `first1` and `last1` are both of type `InputIt1`, which keeps no track of the container (`vector` in our discourse) `first1` and `last1` iterate over.
- On the contrary, the `first1` and `last1` in the *Xlang* version share that explicit “`v1:`” prefix as a part of their type.

Listing 12. `set_difference`'s Type Signature in X

```
set_difference(type T1, type T2, type T3)
    (vector(T1) v1, vector(T2) v2, vector(T3) v3)
    (v1::iterator(T1) first1, v1::iterator(T1) last1,
     v2::iterator(T2) first2, v2::iterator(T2) last2,
     v3::iterator(T3) d_first);
```

In words, [Listing 12](#) is read as follows: Given

- types `T1`, `T2`, and `T3`, and
- vectors `v1`, `v2`, and `v3` of types `vector(T1)`, `vector(T2)`, and `vector(T3)`, respectively, `set_difference` takes
- a pair of iterators `first1` and `last1` which iterate over `v1`,
- a pair of iterators `first2` and `last2` which iterate over `v2`, and
- an iterator `d_first` which iterates over `v3`.

Given that there is no enforcement of sameness for `d_first`, one can indeed drop `v3` to shorten [Listing 12](#) into [Listing 13](#).

Listing 13. More Compact Version of [Listing 12](#)

```
set_difference(type T1, type T2, type T3)(vector(T1) v1, vector(T2) v2)
    (v1::iterator(T1) first1, v1::iterator(T1) last1,
     v2::iterator(T2) first2, v2::iterator(T2) last2,
     iterator(T3) d_first);
```

Section 1.4.2. Why not `std::ranges`?

Some C++ programmers might argue that `iterators` are old technology and that `ranges` solve the problem completely. After all, when one uses a range, one does not specify the two iterators; so, there is no longer a need for making sure they iterate over the same container. Specifying the first iterator of a range and the offset of the second iterator of it is enough. That is why all the C++23 algorithms also

have a `std::ranges` counterpart. Indeed, that is a solution that reduces the possibility of making the same mistake as [Listing 7](#)'s line 02 by simply replacing that line by `sort(first);`.

Unfortunately, contrary to the above C++ belief, that solution only works when the implementation of `std::ranges` for the container of discourse (`vector<int>` in this case) itself does not make the same mistake as line 02 of [Listing 7](#). One can easily produce a **valid** `std::ranges::range`, which make the same mistake, as demonstrated by [Listing 14](#).

[Listing 14](#). A Valid Bad `std::ranges::range`

```
struct BadRange { //This is "valid" C++!  
    vector<int>::iterator begin() {return first.begin();} // Note that it's the begin() of "first" here, ...  
    vector<int>::iterator end()   {return second.end();} // ... whereas, it's the end() of "second" here.  
};  
static_assert(std::ranges::range<BadRange>);
```

Section 1.4.3. What if I don't use `std` algorithms at all?

Even if one only ever uses iterators for manual traversal of containers and avoids the STL algorithms completely, one will have no way in C++ to prevent mistakes **similar to** that of line 02 of [Listing 7](#). For example, C++ cannot detect the mistake of line 04 in [Listing 15](#). That is because C++ has no linguistic support for enforcing the sameness of the containers that `it1` and `it2` iterate over. Again, that is simply because C++ has no linguistic support for instance-specific typing.

[Listing 15](#). The Same Mistake of [Listing 7](#) Even Without a `std` Algorithm

```
01 auto it1 = give_me_an_iterator_from(first);  
02 auto it2 = give_me_another_iterator_from(second);  
03  
04 if (it1 != it2) {...}
```

In order to see how one avoids that in *Xlang*, let us reconsider the body of the `iterator` of [Listing 8](#). Line 04 of [Listing 16](#) adds an `operator !=` to that same `iterator` of [Listing 8](#).

[Listing 16](#). Preventing the Mistake in [Listing 15](#), the X Way

```
01 struct iterator(type T) { // Revisited from Listing 8  
02     unbound vector(T) container;  
03     ...  
04     bool operator != (iterator(T) that) {...}  
05 }
```

```

06
07 it1 := give_me_an_iterator_from(first);
08 it2 := give_me_another_iterator_from(second);
09
10 if (it1 != it2) {...} // compile-error

```

`container` is an `unbound` in the entire scope of `iterator`. In particular, `container` is the same `unbound` in the signature and the body of `operator !=` as the rest of `iterator`. Therefore, `that` and `this` in the body of `iterator.operator !=` are guaranteed to have the same binding for `container`. As a result, the condition on line 10 of [Listing 16](#) fails to type-check for the same reason line 14 of [Listing 8](#) fails to type-check.

Section 1.5. Less Memory Consumption

Consider a routing protocol's implementation. A simplified version of that might devise:

- A cache at each DNS. Let us say, in C++, that would be a `std::hash_map<std::string, IP>`.
- A set of DNSes for each ISP to keep up-to-date. Let us say, in C++, that is a `std::set<DNS>`.

Equating `std::hash_map<std::string, IP>` and `DNS`, each ISP will become `std::set<std::hash_map<std::string, IP>>`. One is likely to want to give all those `std::strings`, `std::hash_maps`, and `std::sets` a common pool due to efficiency reasons. (C++ programmers identify the famous [PMR](#) situation here.) [Listing 17](#) is one possible way to achieve that in C++:

- Implement a memory pool that is efficient for the application at hand (line 01).
- Give each instance of `std::string`, `std::hash_map`, and `std::set` a pointer to an instance of that memory pool (lines 07, 12, and 17).

[Listing 17. Per-Instance Pointer to the Memory Pool](#)

```

01 struct memory_pool {...};
02
03 memory_pool my_mp;
04
05 struct string {
06     ...
07     memory_pool* mpp;
08 };
09
10 template<typename K, typename V> struct hash_map {
11     ...
12     memory_pool* mpp;
13 };

```

```

14
15  template<typename T> struct set {
16      ...
17      memory_pool* mpp;
18  };
19
20  namespace protocol {
21      using DNS = hash_map<string, IP>;
22      using ISP = set<DNS>;
23  }

```

Individually, pointers are quite cheap. However, let us say that there are 10^5 addresses at each DNS. Let's also say that there are 10^2 DNSes in each ISP. With only 10 ISPs, that is a total of 10^8 pointers. In today's technology, pointers are typically 8 Bytes. So, with the pointer-per-instance technology of [Listing 17](#), that is a total of 8MB for the pointers.

In *Xlang*, however, one uses **unbounds** instead of the above pointers. As demonstrated in [Listing 18](#), the *Xlang* counterpart of each of `std::string`, `std::hash_map`, and `std::set` will have an **unbound** that will be bound to the single memory pool at the application layer (lines 20–22). **unbounds** are not owned by their enclosing scope. Neither are they owned by the enclosing scope in which they are bound. Instead, in the call graph, whenever a binding (of an **unbound**) is required, the binding will be added to the call as a hidden argument. Even in the very unlikely case that the call graph becomes 10^2 levels deep, it is 800B using **unbounds** in *Xlang* ([Listing 18](#)) vs 8MB using the pointers in C++ ([Listing 17](#)).

[Listing 18](#). **unbounds** Bound to a Memory Pool

```

01  struct memory_pool {...}
02
03  struct string {
04      ...
05      unbound memory_pool mp;
06  }
07
08  struct hash_map(type K, type V) {
09      ...
10      unbound memory_pool mp;
11  }
12
13  struct set(type T) {
14      ...
15      unbound memory_pool mp;
16  }
17

```

```

18 zone protocol {
19     memory_pool mp;
20     bind string.mp => mp;
21     bind hash_map.mp => mp;
22     bind set.mp => mp;
23     ...
24 }

```

Section 1.6. No Boilerplate Serialization/Deserialization

Serialization of data structures with pointers is bound to face the following difficulty: The content of a pointer itself is an address in the memory. Putting that piece of information in the serialization is not helpful because, in the deserialization, one cannot guarantee that the same address will be given to that particular pointer. Hence, it is the pointee that matters. Copying the pointee all around in the serialization is not economical either and will partly defeat the purpose of using a pointer in the first place. The typical circumvention is embedding an additional table in the serialization, which assigns a unique symbol (usually in the form of a number) to every pointer in the data structure. Upon deserialization, the corresponding pointer will be given an address from memory, by which every occurrence of the respective index of the additional table in the serialized data structure will be replaced.

[Listing 19](#). The Skeleton of a Graph (Consisting of Vertices and Edges) in C

```

struct Vertex {...};

struct Edge {
    ...
    Vertex* begin;
    Vertex* end;
};

```

For example, each edge in [Listing 19](#) has two pointers for its two endpoints: `begin` and `end`. However, using the *Xlang unbounds* ([Listing 20](#)), the programmer already implements the extra table for free (line 01) and makes each vertex a simple wrapper around its index in the table (lines 02–06). This will make vertices particularly cheap to copy to the extent that edges can simply own two vertices for their two endpoints (lines 10 and 11) – instead of pointers to them. Serialization and deserialization are now automatic!

[Listing 20](#). The X Counterpart of [Listing 19](#) using `unbounds`

```

01 struct VertexTable {...};
02 struct Vertex {

```

```

03     ...
04     unbound VertexTable vt;
05     const usize index;//in vt
06 }
07
08 struct edge {
09     ...
10     Vertex begin;
11     Vertex end;
12 }

```

Section 1.7 Considerably Less Keystrokes

One way the C++ programmers may find `unbounds` familiar is their similarity to (type/non-type) template parameters. Consider the struct `S` in [Listing 31](#).

[Listing 31](#). Simple C++ struct with a Type Parameter

```

template<typename T> struct S {};

S<int> s;

```

One can translate that into *Xlang* as in [Lising 32](#) with type parameters or as in [Listing 33](#) with `unbounds`.

[Listing 32](#). *Xlang* Equivalent of [Listing 31](#) with Type Parameters

```

struct STP(type T) {}

STP(int16) stp;

```

[Listing 33](#). *Xlang* Equivalent of [Listing 31](#) with `unbounds`

```

struct SU {unbound type T;}

SU su; // The binding of SU.T has to still be provided from elsewhere.

```

The advantage of [Listing 33](#) over [Listing 32](#) is that the `bind`-resolution rules allow the instantiation of `SU` without the provision of a binding for `SU.T` **at this point**. (As explained in [Section 1.3](#), that binding will still need to be provided at some point in the lexical scope or on the call chain. Otherwise, the code is ill-formed.) The difference might initially be valued as saving a small number of keystrokes. However, the real value of that saving will be appreciated when working with real-world data structures that take

multiple template parameters. For example, [Listing 34](#) shows the C++ synopsis for `flat_map` in addition to the `erase_if` function for `flat_map`.

[Listing 34. `std::flat_map` with its `erase_if` in C++](#)

```
template
<
  class Key, class T, class Compare = less<Key>, class KeyContainer = vector<Key>,
  class MappedContainer = vector<T>
>
class flat_map {...};

template
<
  class Key, class T, class Compare, class KeyContainer, class MappedContainer,
  class Predicate
>
typename flat_map<Key, T, Compare, KeyContainer, MappedContainer>::size_type
erase_if(flat_map<Key, T, Compare, KeyContainer, MappedContainer>& c,
        Predicate pred);
```

If one uses `unbounds` instead of type parameters to transliterate [Listing 34](#) into *Xlang*, one gets to [Listing 35](#).

[Listing 35. Using `unbounds` Instead of Type Parameters for the X Equivalent of \[Listing 34\]\(#\)](#)

```
struct flatMap {
  unbound type Key;
  unbound type T;
  unbound type Compare;
  unbound type KeyContainer;
  unbound type MappedContainer;
  ...
}

flatMap.SizeType eraseIf(type Predicate)(ref flatMap c, Predicate pred);
```

`eraseIf` in [Listing 35](#) is orders of magnitude shorter than `erase_if` in [Listing 34](#) for its lack of the inevitable repetition of template parameters imposed by `std::flat_map` in C++. The header `<flat_map>` of the Standard C++ 2023 has **36** occasions in its interface where such considerable savings are possible. This magnitude of saving is more likely when writing generic libraries.

The *Xlang* **unbounds** are not the first language construct with that benefit. ML abstract types have had that since the late 70s. In the more recent languages, Scala abstract members (i.e., abstract **vals** for data members, abstract **defs** for member functions, and abstract **types**) too have that benefit.

Section 2. Multi-Staged Efficiency and Elegance

The purpose of this section is to introduce the concept of precomputability to the reader. [Section 2.1](#) focuses on demonstrating how the resulting efficiency of precomputation is accessible to the everyday programmer. [Section 2.2](#) is a brief summary of how precompute-time programming provides efficiency that is beyond the familiar compile-time programming. [Section 2.3](#) is for the programming languages specialist; in particular, for those who are familiar with the idea of multi-staged programming.

The main idea in multi-staged programming is efficiency via instructing even more partial evaluation than the compile-time vs runtime dichotomy. The programming cost of multi-staged programming has thus far been so high, however, that the idea never materialized to mainstream programming. [Section 2.3](#) shows how, unlike the familiar multi-staged programming languages, the cost of multi-staging using precomputation is particularly low in *Xlang* – next to zero, to be more precise. As such, multi-staged programming is also elegant in *Xlang*.

Section 2.1. Efficiency for the Everyday Programmer

Let us consider the following example using *Xlang*'s precompute to automatically generate extremely efficient string matcher-code from patterns such as grammars, regular-expressions, etc. The goal is to match subject-strings that start with 'x', followed by one or more non-newline characters, and end with 'z'. The usage will be as in [Listing 36](#), where `match()` is declared to use code-generation guided by the **known** keyword ([Listing 38](#)). One may be able to obtain the same extremely efficient string matcher generated in other languages too. In particular, in C++, the extraordinarily clever design of the [Boost.Hana](#) library shines as a candidate. But, even in C++, that is a job for a world-class programmer. In contrast to C++ (and other systems programming languages), *Xlang* makes that possible by a simple **known**-qualification of a function parameter. **The main message of this subsection is that, in *Xlang*, getting that extremely efficient piece of code generated is a job for the everyday programmer.**

[Listing 36. Sample Usage of the Precomputation Running Example \(String Matching\)](#)

```
if (match("x.*z", subject)) { ... }
```

The post-precompute matcher-code ([Listing 37](#)) is close to what a human might optimize by hand, while the source code fed into the *Xlang* build toolchain ([Listing 38](#)) is fairly straightforward and does not contain any "optimizations." It is reasonable to assume that an everyday programmer will be capable of writing the latter code. *Xlang* brings the efficiency of the former human-optimized code to the everyday programmer that only writes the latter straightforward code.

Xlang automatically transforms `match("x.*z", subject)` of [Listing 36](#) into something functionally equivalent to `match_x_dot_star_z(subject)` in [Listing 37](#).

Listing 37. Possible Precompute Output for the String Matching of the Pattern "x.*z"

```
bool match_x_dot_star_z(ref string subject) {
    if (subject.len && subject[0] == 'x') { // starts with 'x'?
        usize i = 1;
        while (i < subject.len && subject[i] != '\n') { // skip non-newlines
            ++i;
        }
        while (i >= 1) {
            if (i < subject.len && subject[i] == 'z') { // back-up until the last 'z'
                return true; // success: found a 'z'
            }
            --i;
        }
    }
    return false;
}
```

Note how similar the code in [Listing 37](#) is to what a human might author by-hand whilst that gets produced from a template with around 20 lines of fairly obvious source-code, as will be shown in the rest of this section. [Listing 38](#) is the `match()` that is fed into the *Xlang* build toolchain and gets transformed into the human-like code in [Listing 37](#) that is exclusively written for matching "x.*z".

Listing 38. The String Matcher Fed into the *Xlang* Build Toolchain

```

01 bool match(known string pattern, ref string subject) {
02     return match_rest(pattern, 0, subject, 0);
03 }
04
05 // true IFF pattern-substring pattern[p...] matches subject-substring subject[i...]
06 bool match_rest(known string pattern, known mut usize p, ref string subject, usize i) {
07     if (p == pattern.len) return true; // success: no more pattern-chars to match
08
09     // parse pattern's character-specifier: x, ., etc.
10     char c = pattern[p++]; // c is the current pattern-char; it is automatically precomputed
11     static_assert(c != '*' && c != '+' && c != '?', f"{pattern;src}: expected '_{c}'");
12
13     // parse pattern's loop-quantifier: x*, x+, x?
14     usize min, max; // min/max number of c-matches
15     if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '?') { min = 0; max = 1; ++p; } // x?
16     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '*') { min = 0; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; } // x*
17     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '+') { min = 1; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; } // x+
18     else { min = 1; max = 1; } // x
19
20     // match/consume up to max c's:
21     if (min && i + min > subject.len) return false; // no hope if fewer than min chars left
22     usize n = 0; // n is the number of c's matched; nmax is the max# c's we want to match
23     const usize nmax = max == usize.maxVal || i + max > subject.len ? subject.len - i : max;
24     if (c == '.') while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] != '\n') ++n;
25     else while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == c) ++n;
26
27     // pseudo-recurse for the rest of the pattern, "backing out" of c's if needed:
28     if (max == min) return n == min && match_rest(pattern, p, subject, i + min); // x
29     for (j := n + 1; j > min; --j) {
30         if (match_rest(pattern, p, subject, i + j - 1)) return true; // x*
31     }
32     return false;
33 }

```

The `known` qualification of the `pattern` parameters of `match` and `match_rest` makes those parameters like a template parameter in its C++ terms. The key difference is that, unlike C++ template parameters that are compile-time, `pattern` here is a *precompute-time* parameter. The similarity between `pattern` and a C++ template parameter is in that the *Xlang* build toolchain generates as many template instantiations for `match_rest` as it takes, based on the value of `pattern` (and, therefore, `p`) – just like what a C++ compiler does for automatic partial template specializations.

In what follows, we will present template instantiations of `match_rest` (of [Listing 38](#)) that are caused by the invocation `match("x.*z", subject)` in [Listing 36](#). In C++, compiler-generated (partial) template specializations usually have mingled names that are internal to the compiler. Those mingled names usually contain parts from the template parameters that are being specialized. In the same

tradition, we will call the template instantiations of `match_rest` for the invocation `match("x.*z", subject)`: `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_0`, `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_1`, `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_3`, and `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_4`. (The lack of a `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_2` is indeed intentional. The reason will be explained immediately after [Listing 42](#).)

When the *Xlang* build toolchain sees the `match("x.*z", subject)`, it automatically generates a template instantiation for `match_rest`, which is functionally equivalent to the [Listing 39](#): (Color-coding: `pattern "x.*z"` means the original source-code `pattern` was precomputed-and-replaced by value `"x.*z"`. The same color-coding is also used for the rest of this section.)

[Listing 39](#). Template Instantiation of `match` in [Listing 38](#) for the `match("x.*z", subject)` Invocation

```
bool match_x_dot_star_z(ref string subject) {
    return match_rest(pattern "x.*z", 0, subject, 0);
}
```

[Listing 39](#), in return, will get the build toolchain to generate `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_0` in [Listing 40](#): (The highlighted strike-through portions optimized out when there is no green backgrounded code to the right of them. Again, we will continue using the color-coding for the rest of this section.)

Listing 40. `match_rest` Template Instantiated for `pattern == "x.*z"` and (Initially) `p == 0`

```

01 bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_0(ref string subject, usize i) {
02     if (p == pattern.len) return true;
03     char c = pattern[p+1] 'x'; // N.B., p == 1 at this point!
04     static_assert(c != '*' && c != '?' && c != '?', ...);
05
06     usize min, max;
07     if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '?') { ++p; min = 0; max = 1; }
08     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '*') { ++p; min = 0; max = usize.maxVal; }
09     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '?') { ++p; min = 1; max = usize.maxVal; }
10     else { min = 1; max = 1; }
11
12     if (min && i + min > subject.len) return false;
13     usize n = 0;
14     const usize nmax = max == usize.maxVal || i + max > subject.len ? subject.len - i : max;
15     if (c == '.') while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] != '\n') ++n;
16     else while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == c 'x') ++n;
17
18     if (max == min) return n == min && match_rest(pattern "x.*z", p, subject, i + min);
19     for (j := n + 1; j > min; --j) if (rest(pattern, p, subject, i + j - 1)) return true;
20     return false;
21 }

```

It is noteworthy that `n`, in [Listing 40](#), is (myopically) runtime. That is because, on line 16, `n` is updated in the body of `while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == 'x') ++n`; and any variable updated within a loop is dependent on the loop's conditional. Therefore, `n` has a dependency on `n < nmax && subject[i + n] == 'x'`. But, `n < nmax && subject[i + n] == 'x'` itself is dependent on `subject` and `i`, both of which being non-known-qualified formal-parameters, and, hence, runtime.

The other noteworthy point about `match` and `match_rest` is that there will be even more precompute-time optimization for a fully-precomputable call to those two functions, i.e., when they are invoked using precomputable arguments. This document will not go through those additional optimizations, however.

Removing the strike-through portions of [Listing 40](#), one gets to what is in [Listing 41](#).

Listing 41. [Listing 40](#) After the Removal of Strike-through Portions

```

bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_0(ref string subject, usize i) {
    return i + 1 < subject.len && subject[i] == 'x' &&
        match_rest("x.*z", 1, subject, i + 1);
}

```

```
}
```

The call to `match_rest` inside the `return`-statement of [Listing 41](#) produces another template instantiation for `match_rest`; this time with `p == 1` (and `subject == "x.*z"`), as shown in [Listing 42](#).

Listing 42. `match_rest` Template Instantiated for `pattern == "x.*z"` and (Initially) `p == 1`

```
01 bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_1(ref string subject, size i) {
02     if (p == pattern.len) return true;
03     char c = pattern[p++]; // N.B., p==2 at this point!
04     static_assert(c != '*' && c != '+' && c != '?', f"{pattern;src}: expected '_{c}'");
05
06     using min, max;
07     if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '?') { min = 0; max = 1; ++p; }
08     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '*') { min = 0; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; p = 3; } // N.B., p==3
09     else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '+') { min = 1; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; }
10     else { min = 1; max = 1; }
11
12     if (min && i + min > subject.len) return false;
13     using n = 0;
14     const using nmax = max == usize.maxVal || i + max > subject.len ? subject.len - i : max;
15     if (c == '?') while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] != '\n') ++n;
16     else while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == c) ++n;
17
18     if (max == min) return n == min && match_rest(pattern, p, subject, i + min);
19     for (j := n + 1; j > min; --j) if (match_rest(pattern "x.*z", p 3, subject, i + j - 1)) return true;
20     return false;
21 }
```

Similar to [Listing 40](#), `n` in [Listing 42](#) is (myopically) runtime. Because, its value depends on the condition of the `while` loop on line 14; but, that condition depends on `subject` and `i`, which are both runtime. It is also noteworthy that, in [Listing 42](#), `i` gets incremented twice: on lines 03 and 08. That is why there are template instantiations of `match_rest` for `i == 1` and `i == 3` but not for `i == 2`.

After the removal of the strike-through and unused variable elimination, one gets from [Listing 42](#) to [Listing 43](#).

Listing 43. [Listing 42](#) After Clean-up

```

01 bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_1(ref string subject, usize i) {
02     n := 0uz;
03     const nmax := subject.len - i;
04     while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] != '\n') ++n;
05     for (j := n + 1; j > 0; --j) if (match_rest("x.*z", 3, subject, i + j - 1))
06         return true;
07     return false;
08 }

```

Again, the call to `match_rest` on line 05 of [Listing 43](#) generates the `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_3` template instantiation in [Listing 44](#). (Recall that there will not be any `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_2` because `p` is incremented twice in `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_1`; see lines 03 and 08 of [Listing 42](#).)

Listing 44. `match_rest` Template Instantiation for `pattern == "x.*z"` and (Initially) `p == 3` (As Opposed to `p == 2`)

```

bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_3(ref string subject, usize i) {
    if (p == pattern.len) return true;

    char c = pattern[p++] 'z'; // N.B., p == 4 at this point!
    static_assert(c != '*' && c != '+' && c != '?', f"{pattern;src}: expected '_{c}'");

    usize min, max;
    if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '?') { min = 0; max = 1; ++p; }
    else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '*') { min = 0; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; }
    else if (p != pattern.len && pattern[p] == '+') { min = 1; max = usize.maxVal; ++p; }
    else { min = 1; max = 1; }

    if (min && i + min > subject.len) return false;
    usize n = 0;
    const usize nmax = max == usize.maxVal || i + max > subject.len ? subject.len - i : max;
    if (c == '.') while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] != '\n') ++n;
    else while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == c) ++n;

    if (max == min) return n == min && match_rest(pattern "x.*z", p, subject, i + min);
    for (j := n + 1; j > min; --j) if (match_rest(pattern, p, subject, i + j - 1)) return true;
    return false;
}

```

After strikethrough and unused variable removal, one gets from [Listing 44](#) to [Listing 45](#).

Listing 45. [Listing 44](#) After Clean-up

```

01 bool match_rest_x_dot_star_z_3(ref string subject, usize i) {

```

```

02     if (i + 1uz > subject.len) return false;
03     usize n = 0uz;
04     const usize nmax = i + 1uz > subject.len ? subject.len - i : 1uz;
05     while (n < nmax && subject[i + n] == 'z') ++n;
06     return n == 1uz && match_rest("x.*z", 4, subject, i + 1uz);
07 }

```

Again, the call to `match_rest` on line 06 of `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_3` in [Listing 45](#) generates `match_rest_x_dot_star_z_4` in [Listing 46](#).

[Listing 46.](#) `match_rest` Template Instantiation for `pattern == "x.*z"` and (Initially) `p == 4`

```

bool match_rest_x_dot_star_4(ref string subject, usize i) {
    if (p == pattern.len) return true;
}

```

Finally, `match_rest_x_dot_star_1`, `match_rest_x_dot_star_3`, and `match_rest_x_dot_star_4` are all non-recursive and relatively simple. They can be inline-expanded to the code shown in [Listing 47](#).

[Listing 47.](#) Putting `match_rest_x_dot_star_1`, `match_rest_x_dot_star_3`, and `match_rest_x_dot_star_4` Together

```

bool match_x_dot_star_z(ref string subject) {
    if (subject.len && subject[0] == 'x') {
        usize i = 1;
        while (i < subject.len && subject[i] != '\n') {
            ++i;
        }
        while (i >= 1) {
            if (i < subject.len && subject[i] == 'z') {
                return true;
            }
            --i;
        }
    }
    return false;
}

```

Section 2.2. Efficiency Beyond the Reach of C/C++

The astute reader wonders: What in [Section 2.1](#) sets precompute-time apart from compile-time? After all, "x.*z" in [Listing 36](#) is already available at compile-time too. So, the availability to the everyday programmer aside, obtaining all the results of Section 2.1 should, in principle, be possible at compile-time. In fact, that is a correct observation. Yet, a conclusion on precompute-time not having an added value in the presence of compile-time will not be correct.

In order to demonstrate the efficiency that precomputation offers that is beyond compile-time – and, therefore, unavailable to C/C++ or any of the existing systems programming languages of this time – we would like to invite the reader to consider the code in [Listing 48](#).

[Listing 48. Loading the Pattern from a File](#)

```
known string pattern = read_from_my_file();
if (match(pattern, subject)) { ... }
```

Typically, File I/O is not possible at compile-time. Such are also network or database reads. That is why [Listing 48](#) is currently beyond C/C++, Zig, etc. At precompute-time, though, that is possible because precompute-time is like a preamble to the runtime. In fact, like every other compiled language, the *Xlang* compiler only partially evaluates the source code. Unlike the other compiled languages, however, after having performed operations that are to be done at precompute-time (like the above *known*-qualified file I/O), the accordingly adjusted source code may get looped back into the compiler until there remains no such operations and the final object code is delivered. For example, after having obtained the result of `read_from_my_file()` to be "x.*z", the *Xlang* build toolchain can simplify [Listing 48](#) into [Listing 36](#), which results in template instantiations presented in the previous section.

Section 2.3. Precompute-Time: A New Stage Between Compile-Time and Runtime

A common motivating example in the multi-stage programming languages is that, in the OCaml code of [Listing 49](#), every call to `power2` causes a call to `power` and recursive calls; whereas, one *knows* that `power2(x)` is simply $1 * x * x$. As an example from a multi-staging programming language, [Listing 50](#) shows the same code augmented with staging in MetaOCaml. `power2(x)` in [Listing 50](#) indeed reduces to $1 * x * x$.

[Listing 49. OCaml Code for an Exponentiation Function and its Special Case for Squares](#)

```
let rec power (n, x) =
  match n with
  0 -> 1 | n -> x * (power (n - 1, x));;
```

```
let power2 (x) = power (2, x);;
```

In addition to the OCaml syntax itself being daunting to the vast majority of systems programmers of nowadays, the staging syntax of MetaOCaml can be particularly tricky for even the seasoned OCaml programmers. Upon programming languages like MetaOCaml, one has to be scrupulously careful with the positioning of the staging elements, i.e., bracketing/quoting, splicing, and running (“.<...>.”, “.~”, and “.!””, respectively, in MetaOCaml) for two very distinct reasons:

- Firstly, failing to place the staging element at the right position can suddenly produce notorious typing disagreements between the programmer’s intentions and what the compiler makes of their code. Detective work on the root cause of such disagreements is nontrivial and requires tool support that is beyond the typical build toolchain of a language.
- Secondly, even when the programmer does manage to settle those typing disagreements, simple mispositioning of the logic inside quotes versus outside them can quietly introduce unexpectedly harsh performance penalties that are even more difficult to demystify.

Listing 50. MetaOCaml Code for Staging the Code in [Listing 49](#)

```
let rec power (n, x) =  
  match n with  
  0 -> .<1>. | n -> .<~x * .~(power (n - 1, x))>.;;  
  
let power2 = .! .<fun x -> .~(power (2, .<x>.)>.;;
```

Part of the latter difficulty is due to the lack of a profiler for staging. For example, as shown by Taha⁴, the code in [Listing 50](#) is a so-called *Jones-Optimal* partial evaluation for the code in [Listing 49](#). However, Taha himself (as the author of MetaOCaml) reports, in another code of his, that placing an `if`-statement inside a quote causes four times degradation in the performance. In order to figure out the reason, he invites the reader to *look into* the OCaml output of MetaOCaml for the code with the misplaced `if`-statement. Taha’s text does not clarify how that generated OCaml is obtained.

The other part of the difficulty is that, with bare staging, the programmer of the staged code is obliged to reinvent the wheel for a lot of the compiler’s bread-and-butter. For example, even when the misplacing is discovered, as a solution, Taha shows how to employ continuations, which makes the MetaOCaml even more involved. Continuations are amongst the common compiler optimization techniques for many functional programming languages. Taha tries to further optimize the staged code with the misplaced `if`-statement using binding-time improvements and enforcing inlining. Again, both binding-time optimization and inlining are in the routine of every compiler nowadays.

In sheer contrast, *Xlang* achieves all those and even much more by a simple `known`-qualification of `power`’s first parameter, as shown in [Listing 51](#).

⁴ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-540-25935-0_3

Listing 51. *Xlang*'s Version of [Listing 50](#)

```
int64 power(known usize n, int64 x) {
    if (n == 0) return 1;
    return x * power(n - 1, x);
}

int64 power2(int64 x) { return power(2, x);}
```

The *Xlang* counterpart is preferable over the MetaOCaml one because:

1. Utilising precomputation is as easy as placing a single `known` keyword in front of a formal parameter. Contrast that with the heavy syntactic overhead of [Listing 50](#) in comparison to [Listing 49](#). In real-world examples, the heavyweightedness of the typical multi-staging syntax hurts even more.
2. The difference between the type signature of the *Xlang* `power` function with the `known`-qualification for `n` and without it is solely in that same `known`-qualification. That is totally different between normal OCaml and staged MetaOCaml, for example. In MetaOCaml, one needs to be careful with the combinatorial combination of the various manual indirections falling under the `code` type qualifier or outside of it.
3. In order to benefit from multi-staging, the *Xlang* programmer leaves the compiler's job to the *Xlang* build toolchain. This point is two-fold:
 - a. The precompute engine analyzes the code in passes. At every pass, after having performed precompute optimizations, there is a likelihood that the current version of the code is looped back into the compiler. Hence, when it comes to the typical compiler optimizations (e.g., dead-code elimination, unused variable elimination, function call inlining, etc.) the programmer is not required to enforce such optimizations manually. Unlike the other multi-staging programming languages, those are all automatic in *Xlang*. As an example, consider [Listing 52](#) for one pass of precomputation (top) followed by function call inlining (bottom) after looping back into the compiler. One already sees dead-code elimination at the top of [Listing 52](#) even before the inlining. (Contrast [Listing 44](#) with [Listing 45](#) for unused variable elimination.)
 - b. Most of the precompute-time optimization takes place even without `known`-qualification. Indeed, the build toolchain automatically nominates as many code portions as it can for precomputation. At precompute-time, then, those portions get optimized and the resulting code gets fed back to the earlier phases of the *Xlang* build toolchain; this loop continues until there are no new nominees for precomputation.

Conclusion: Precompute-time as a modern stage in its multi-staged programming sense is prominent because it is automatic – both in its application of (the routine compiler) optimizations and the detection of the precomputation nominees.

Listing 52. Precompute Engine's Output of [Listing 51](#) before Inlining (Top) and after Inlining (Bottom)

```
//-----
// Before Inlining
```

```

//-----
int64 power_2(int64 x) {
    if (n == 0) return 1;
    return x * power_1(x);
}

int64 power_1(int64 x) {
    if (n == 0) return 1;
    return x * power_0(x);
}

int64 power_0(int64 x) {
    if (n == 0) return 1;
    return x * power(n - 1, x);
}

//-----
// After Inlining
//-----

int64 power_2(int64 x) {
    return x * x * 1;
}

```

Section 3. Render Tree: Real-Sized Example

The purpose of this example is to demonstrate the power of **unbounds** in a real-sized example. To that end, we invite the reader to take this as a challenge in their favourite programming language and compare the *Xlang* solution given here with that of theirs. Our *Xlang* solution demonstrates the value of **unbounds** as an efficient means with syntactic elegance for sharing entities among a massive number of small objects grouped together in different families. We now move to the statement of the challenge.

In a typical video-game of nowadays, there are a plethora of game objects. The five requirements below (R1–R5) specify the challenge:

- There is a lot of commonality between the interfaces of the game objects. Therefore, coding in terms of the common interface should be facilitated for its high degree of reusability by all the game objects. (R1)
- Game objects have a lot to share in various ways. Some of those shared entities are shared among all the objects in a game; others are shared only among families of game objects. Objects can belong to more than one family; each family having its own shared entities. Such families are distinct in the sense that their similar belongings should be distinguished from one another. Attempts for using such similar belongings interchangeably should be disallowed statically. (R2)

- Serialization and deserialization of such objects should be reverse actions. That is, serialization of a game object followed by deserialization should give an identical copy of the original game object. (R3) Hint:
 - By identical, we do not mean identical modulo pointer/reference values. We mean identical in every belonging of the object.
 - Pointers are not reversible because the address that a pointer points to before serialization will most likely not make the same sense, if any at all, upon deserialization.
- Programming such objects should be elegant, i.e., not involve boilerplate. (R4)
- The solution should not be hardcoded for game objects. That is, the techniques and technologies used should be available to similar problems with a massive number of small objects with the above specification of sharing items among their different families. (R5)

We now move to the *Xlang* solution of this section. For the sake of presentation, we apply the following simplifications.

- Out of all the possible game objects, we narrow our focus to scene objects. Hence, the name render tree in the title of this section.
- All the game objects that are loaded from the same file are in the same family and hence compatible. Game objects loaded from different files are in different families and hence incompatible.
- Shapes are only a polygon of points.

Central to our solution is that instances of game objects do **NOT** store their

- names as data members. All the names of a family are stored in the family's `StringManager`; individual `Strings` – and, hence, the name of every instance of a game object – are only a pair of indices for the beginning and the end of the `String` in the family's `StringManager`.
- shape data as data members. All the shape data of a family is stored in the family's `ShapeData`; individual `Shapes` – and, hence, the shape data of the instances of a game object that have a shape – are only indices in the family's `ShapeData`.

With those two points in mind, we get to [Listing 53](#) for `StringManager` and `String`. Notice how a `String` has an `unbound` called `Mgr` for its family's `StringManager` (line 05).

Listing 53. [StringManager](#) and [String](#)

```
01 zone Strings {
02
03     struct String {
04         unbound StringManager Mgr;
05         int32 stringIndex_;
06
07         String(string s) {
08             stringIndex_ = StringManager.addString(s);
09         }
10         string toSysString() {
11             return Mgr.table_[stringIndex_];
12         }
13         int32 length() {
14             return Mgr.table_[stringIndex_].len;
15         }
16         char getChar(int32 atIndex) {
17             return Mgr.table_[stringIndex_][atIndex];
18         }
19     }
20
21     struct StringManager {
22         string[] table_;
23
24         // Creates a string or inserts it into the table, returns its index
25         int32 addString(string s) {
26             for (i := 0; i < table_.len; i++) {
27                 if (table_[i] == s)
28                     return i;
29             }
30             table_ += s;
31             return table_.len - 1;
32         }
33
34         void load(ref mut SysFile f) {
35             // read array, assumes this can read/write arrays of any serializable type
36             f.readBinTypes(table_);
37         }
38         void save(ref mut SysFile f) {
39             // write array
40             f.writeBinTypes(table_);
41         }
42     }
43 }
```

Given [Listing 53](#) and the contents of the previous sections, the reader is expected to be able to understand [Listing 54](#) for `ShapeData` and `Shape`.

Listing 54. `ShapeData` and `Shape`

```
01 zone Shapes {
02
03     struct ShapeData {
04         struct ShapeRecord {
05             int32[pointCount_] pointIndex_;
06             int32                pointCount_;
07         }
08
09         Point[] points_;
10         ShapeRecord[] records_;
11
12         void display(ref mut Renderer renderer, int32 shapeIndex, int32 c) {
13             ref rec := records_[shapeIndex];
14             renderer.renderShape(points_, rec.pointIndex_, rec.pointCount_, c);
15         }
16
17         void load(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
18         void save(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
19     }
20
21     struct Shape {
22         unbound ShapeData Data;
23
24         Point offset_;
25         int32 shapeRecordIndex_;
26         int32 color_;
27
28         void render(ref mut Renderer renderer) {
29             renderer.pushOffset(offset_);
30             Data.display(renderer, shapeRecordIndex_, color_);
31             renderer.popOffset();
32         }
33         void load(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
34         void save(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
35     }
36
37     // ShapeGroup is a set of shapes that can all be drawn as a unit.
38     // Also one can append group items to each other.
39
40     struct ShapeGroup {
```

```

41     (&Shape)[] shapes_;
42     Point offset_;
43
44     void addShape(&Shape s) {
45         shapes_ += s;
46     }
47     void appendShapeGroup(ref ShapeGroup s) {
48         shapes_ += s.shapes_;
49     }
50
51     void render(ref mut Renderer renderer) {
52         renderer.pushOffset(offset_);
53         for (s in shapes_) {
54             shapes_.display(renderer);
55         }
56         renderer.popOffset();
57     }
58     void load(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
59     void save(ref mut SysFile f) { ... }
60 }
61 } // zone Shapes

```

Again, notice how each `Shape` keeps track of its family's `ShapeData` using the `unbound` scoped inside it that is called `Data` (line 22).

R3 and R4 are already fulfilled in [Listing 53](#) and [Listing 54](#) because:

- Instances of `Shape` and `String` are particularly lightweight. They are not more than a few indices. See [Section 1.5](#) on the positive contribution of `unbounds` in `Shape` and `String` being lightweight.
- Serialization and deserialization of `Shape` and `String` are trivial and elegant at the same time that they are total reverse actions. Serialization of `ShapeData` and `StringManager` is a simple dump of the data in the same order they are in memory; their deserialization, on the other hand, is loading the same data from disk and in the same order. Besides, that sameness of order implies that the same indices of `String` and `Shape` instances prior to serialization are used for deserialization. See [Section 1.6](#) for more.

As a demonstration of R1's fulfillment, consider [Listing 55](#), where `SceneObject` is a `trait` (as opposed to a `struct` in [Listing 5](#)). The location of a scene object is determined by its `offset_` (line 04). The intention behind the member functions `display`, `load`, and `save` (lines 04–06) should be self-explanatory.

We assume a number of scene object structs implementing `SceneObject`. Examples are `TextualObject` (line 14), `ShapefulObject` (line 15), and `SOContainer` (line 16) used in [Listing 56](#). The implementation of those structs are, however, omitted here for brevity.

Listing 55. Variation of [Listing 5's SceneObject](#)

```
01 trait SceneObject {
02     using Strings.String, Shapes.Shape;
03
04     Point offset_;
05     String name_;
06     Shape shape_;
07
08     void display(ref mut Renderer renderer);
09
10     void load(ref mut File f);
11     void save(ref mut File f);
12 }
13
14 struct TextualObject impl SceneObject {...}
15 struct ShapefulObject impl SceneObject {...}
16 struct SOContainer impl SceneObject {...}
```

Structs implementing `SceneObject` will need to provide data members or properties for `name_` and `shape_`, in particular, which are instances of `String` and `Shape`, respectively (lines 05 and 06 of [Listing 55](#)). Recall, however, that both `String` ([Listing 53](#)) and `Shape` ([Listing 54](#)) have `unbounds` declared in their bodies. Hence, instances of the structs that implement `SceneObject` need to be supplied with bindings for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape`. Here, we take `S0Files` to supply those bindings, as shown in [Listing 56](#). (The leading “S0” part of `S0File` is for `SceneObject`.)

Listing 56. Files bind the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape`

```
01 // ***** S0File combines the use of containers and
02
03 struct S0File {
04     // String and Shape Tables.
05     Strings.StringManager manager_;
06     Shapes.ShapeData sdata_;
07
08     bind Strings.String.Mgr => manager_;
09     bind Shapes.Shape.Data => sdata_;
10
11     // Scene graph. Note: SOContainer not presented here for brevity.
12     SOContainer scene_;
13
14     void display(ref mut Renderer renderer) {
15         scene_.display(renderer);
16     }
```

```

17
18     bool load(ref mut SysFile f) {
19         manager_.load(f);
20         sdata_.load(f);
21         scene_.load(f);
22         return true;
23     }
24     bool save(ref mut SysFile f) {
25         manager_.save(f);
26         sdata_.save(f);
27         scene_.save(f);
28         return true;
29     }
30
31     dyn& SceneObject findObject(string s) {
32         return scene_.findNamedObject(String{s});
33     }
34
35     &TextualObject findTextObject(string s) {
36         return scene_.findNamedObject(String{s}) as &TextualObject;
37     }
38     &ShapefulObject findShapeObject(string s) {
39         return scene_.findNamedObject(String{s}) as &ShapefulObject;
40     }
41 }

```

In addition to `S0File`, one can bind `Strings.String.Mgr` and `Shapes.Shape.Data` in any scope one likes. That innermost enclosing scope of a binding is where a family sharing that `unbound` is formed. In the very case of `S0Files` representing families, the reader is invited to pay attention to the `binds` on lines 08 and 09. Both those `binds` are instance-specific. (Because, they are bound to data members of `S0File`.) That is what enables us to fulfill R2, as will be demonstrated in [Listing 57](#).

A bit of explanation is required at this point regarding the new pieces of *Xlang* syntax used in [Listing 56](#):

- Where `T` is a type, `&T` signifies the type of an owned reference to `T`. Such references can take the `null` value. Given an instance `r` of them, `if(r)` checks whether `r` is `null`.
- Where `Tau` is a trait, `dyn& Tau` signifies the type of an owned reference to a type that `impls` the trait `Tau`. The “`dyn`” part of `dyn& Tau` signifies the dynamic binding (aka late-binding) provided to the member functions in the interface of `Tau`.

Those two pieces of syntax are used on lines 31, 35, and 38 in [Listing 56](#). In [Listing 57](#), we will use `dyn ref Tau`, which is similar to `dyn& Tau` in its dynamic binding for the member functions in `Tau`'s interface. The difference is that the former is a lifetime reference. Listing 57 also uses another new piece of *Xlang* syntax:

- For an expression `e` and a type `T`, the expression `e as T` is a dynamic cast operation that reduces to a `T&`. A `null` result represents unsuccessful casting.

Listing 57. Sample Usage of `S0File` and the Requirement R2

```
001 int64 main() {
002     S0File f1, f2;
003
004     // f1 and f2 come from two separate files
005     // and thus have distinct StringManager Tables and display trees.
006     if (!f1.load(SysFile{"file1.ext", read = true}))
007         return 1;
008     if (!f2.load(SysFile{"file2.ext", read = true}))
009         return 1;
010
011     // ***** Example 1 -- Creating File-local objects
012
013     f1t := new f1:TextualShape{"hello", 5, 6};
014     f1.scene_.add(f1t);
015     f2.scene_.add(new f2:TextualShape{"hello2", 10, 12});
016
017     t := f2.findTextObject("item");
018     if (t) {
019         // Change position of item.
020         t.Offset.x += 1;
021
022         // Make a clone, and add it back
023         f2t := new f2:TextualShape(t);
024
025         // f1.scene_.add(f2t);
026         // Error!
027         // * f1:Strings.String.Mgr == f1.manager_ != f2:Strings.String.Mgr ==
028         f2.manager_ and
029         // * f1:Shapes.Shape.Data == f1.sdata_ != f2:Shapes.Shape.Data ==
030         f2.sdata_
031
032         f2.scene_.add(f2t);
033
034         // *** Calling same adjustTextNode function on objects from both files
035         adjustTextNode(f1t);
036         // ok, calls f1:adjustTextNode(f1t)
037
038         adjustTextNode(f2t);
039         // ok, calls f2:adjustTextNode(f2t)
040
```

```

041     // adjustTextNode2(f1t, f2t);
042     // Error! Implicit bind-sameness assumption failure for f1t and f2t.
043 }
044
045 // ***** Example 2 -- Treating Files consistently
046
047 // We can display files treating them identically!
048
049 ref SOFile[] files = {f1, f2};
050 renderFiles(files);
051
052 // Error: mismatching bindings of SOContainer
053 // ref SOContainer[] containers1 = { f1.scene_, f2.scene_ };
054 // renderFileContainerScenes(containers1);
055
056 // Ok for one object, but must ':' qualify.
057 ref f1:SOContainer[] containers1 = { f1.scene_ };
058 f1:renderFileContainerScenes(containers1);
059
060 dyn ref SceneObject[] containers;
061 // Error - mismatching binding
062 //containers += f1.scene_;
063 // Error - mismatching binding
064 // containers += f2.scene_;
065
066 // This is ok:
067 dyn ref f1:SceneObject[] containers1 = { f1.scene_ };
068 // But you won't be able to add the other binding type
069 // Error - mismatching type
070 // containers1 += f2.scene_;
071
072 /// ***** Example 3 -- ShapeData
073
074 // You can manipulate and reuse shape-groups within the same file
075 // but not across files
076
077 // Allow writer to omit 'f1:' which is implied when returned
078 &ShapeGroup g1 = f1.findObject("shapeGroup1") as ShapeGroup;
079 &ShapeGroup g2 = f1.findObject("shapeGroup2") as ShapeGroup;
080 if (g1 && g2) {
081     // Make a new Shape group from two and add them to the new object!!
082     ShapeGroup g3 = new f1:ShapeGroup;
083     g3.Name = "shapeGroup3";
084     g3.Shapes.appendShapeGroup(g1.Shapes);
085     g3.Shapes.appendShapeGroup(g2.Shapes);
086     f1.scene_.add(g3);
087 }

```

```

086
087     &ShapeGroup f2gA = f1.findObject("shapeGroupA") as ShapeGroup;
088     if (g1 && f2gA) {
089         // Make a new Shape group from two and add them to the new object!!
090         ShapeGroup g4 = new f1:ShapeGroup;
091         g4.Name = "shapeGroup4";
092
093         // Error -- mismatching type!!!
094         g4.Shapes.appendShapeGroup(f2gA.Shapes);
095         f1.scene_.add(g4);
096     }
097 }
098
099 // Functions for the examples above
100
101 void adjustTextNode(ref MyText n) {
102     n.Offset.x += 1;
103 }
104 void adjustTextNode2(ref MyText n1, ref MyText n2) {
105     n1.Offset.x = n2.Offset.x + 1;
106 }
107 void renderFiles(ref MyFile[] files, ref Renderer r) {
108     foreach(f in files) {
109         f.display(r);
110     }
111 }
112 void renderFileContainerScenes(ref SOContainer[] containers, ref Renderer r) {
113     foreach(c in containers) {
114         c.display(r);
115     }
116 }
117
118
119
120
121
122
123
124

```

In [Listing 57](#):

- It is legal to add `f1t` to the `scene_` data member of `f1` (line 014) because the file of both `f1t` and `f1.scene_` is `f1`. Recall that that means the bindings supplied for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape` are the same, hence, the compatibility. The situation is similar when adding `f2t` to the `scene_` of `f2` (line 023).

- It is illegal to add `f1t` to the `scene_` data member of `f2` (line 025) because of the `bind`-incompatibility between `f1t` and the `scene_` data member of `f2`. A compile-error will be issued for such an attempt.
- Likewise, it is illegal to pass `f1t` and `f2t` together to `adjustTextNode2` (line 040) because that will violate the `bind`-sameness assumption.

It is important to note that, despite their instance-specific bindings, `f1` and `f2` are still of type `S0File`. Hence, it is perfectly acceptable for `f1` and `f2` to be put together in an array and sent collectively to a function that expects an array of `S0Files` (lines 049—50). Despite that, the types that depend on `f1` and `f2` are incompatible for their reliability on the bindings supplied for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape`. That is why lines 053 and 054 would have been compile errors.

In a similar vein, `containers` on line 061 would have only been legal if

- either the function `main` could have been called and every caller of it supplied its own bindings for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape`. Or,
- the function `main` could have been inside a zone, where bindings for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape` are supplied.

Even in those circumstances, `containers` can only be accumulated with `SceneObjects` the bindings of which for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape` are not supplied by `f1` or `f2`. Like `containers` itself, what's to be accumulated in `containers` has to leave the bindings to the caller of `main` or its enclosing zone. (Note, however, that, like many languages of the C family, `main` is a special function. In particular, it cannot be called from other functions; neither can it be enclosed by other scopes, zone or not.)

Contrary to `containers` on line 061, `containers1` on line 68 is completely legal. However, given that `containers1` takes its bindings for the `unbounds` of `String` and `Shape`, exclusively, any attempt to `SceneObjects` with other bindings to `containers1` (like on line 71) would be a compile-error.